

Characterizing Climate Change Through Heat Index Trends: A Case Study in the Mapalana, Low Country Wet Zone of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Climate change, particularly fluctuations in temperature and relative humidity (RH), significantly influences agriculture. Recent research identifies Sri Lanka as one of the most climate-vulnerable nations globally. Since RH and temperature play vital roles in plant metabolism, growth, and development, variations in these parameters directly affect crop productivity. High RH during nighttime has been shown to increase dry matter production, leaf area, and plant height, while prolonged exposure to high temperature and humidity leads to crop stress. The heat index (HI), which combines air temperature and RH, provides a useful measure of how heat is perceived and the potential stress it places on crops. This study analyzed long-term trends in air temperature, RH, and HI in Mapalana, a representative site in Sri Lanka's Low Country Wet Zone, using 30 years (1992–2022) of daily meteorological data. Monthly and annual HI values were computed using the Rothfusz regression equation. Results indicated that the annual average temperature ranged from 27.23°C to 29.60°C, while RH ranged from 68.30% to 84.02%. HI values fluctuated from 29°C to 39°C, with 1998 recording the highest value above 39°C. Most years showed an annual HI around 35°C. According to the National Weather Service HI classification, these values fall within the "Caution" (27°C–32°C) and "Extreme Caution" (32°C–41°C) categories, indicating an increasing risk of heat stress for crops and human health. Trend analysis confirmed a gradual increase in HI over the study period, signifying escalating heat stress on crops. These findings highlight the urgent need for climate-resilient agricultural strategies, including heat-tolerant crop varieties and adaptive farming practices. The study further provides critical regional insights that can enhance crop modeling and guide agricultural planning in the Low Country Wet Zone of Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Climate change, Heat index, Low country wet zone, Relative humidity, Temperature*